

Tipp City Project, Miami County (39.95910, -84.14392)

Since construction in 2022, the main nutrient benefit of the Tipp City Project has been filtering inflows from the Great Miami River. The dry weather conditions of 2024 had relatively limited effect on the volume of water received by the Project, with the year's total inflow volume in 2024 slightly outpacing that of 2023. However, multiple large flooding events over a short period in April resulted in decreased water storage capacity and shorter residence times, likely accounting for the lower nutrient filtration in 2024 (3.7 lbs phosphorus per acre) as compared to 2023 (11 lbs phosphorus per acre). The Project also contributes 0.7 lbs phosphorus per acre each year from runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, for a total retention of 4.4 lbs phosphorus per acre.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project (10 acres restored wetland) is an off-channel wetland, consisting of a large, permanently flooded pool. Water enters from the Great Miami River via inflow notch and inundates the pool basin. There is no dedicated outflow, but water exits via backflow and likely also subsurface exchange with the river or groundwater. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a flow event when the river discharge rate at the inflow notch reaches approximately 2,627 cubic feet per second, causing river water to flood the wetland pool.

Nutrient Retention

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar off-channel wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- The inflow notch could be lowered to capture flows more frequently from the Great Miami River, but a balance would need to be found between retaining nutrient loads and not inundating the entire Project.
- Vegetation could be planted in the shallower areas of the wetland pool (i.e., elevated flats and around the edge of the pool) as another way to potentially increase nutrient reductions but would require taking into account the appropriate vegetation for expected flooding regime, which may be constrained by sustained drastic changes in water level (i.e., extreme flooding in winter and spring, and drought conditions in summer and fall).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.